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“Prejudice Behaviour of College Going Students Belonging To Hindu, Muslim and Christian Religions: A Comparative Study”.

SUNANDA NANDA BERA,
PH.D. IN EDUCATION (RESEARCH SCHOLAR),
RKDF UNIVERSITY, BHOPAL (M.P.) INDIA.

E-MAIL ID: snbera9@gmail.com

Dr. ALOK SHARMA
THE SUPERVISOR,
RESEARCH GUIDE,
EDUCATION DEPARTMENT,
RKDF UNIVERSITY, BHOPAL - 462033 (M.P.), INDIA.

ABSTRACT

‘Prejudice’ is unfair behavior that results from having fixed opinions or without affecting any other legal matter. Prejudices are of certain inevitable features of human society and play an important role in the undaunted expression of Behavior, when two groups come into face to face relation. The present study intends to measure the Prejudice behavior of college going students belonging to Hindu, Muslim and Christian religions. The total Sample comprises of 120 students (Rural + Urban) was randomly selected from different colleges of Durg and Bilai City of Chhattisgarh State and equally distributed among Hindu, Muslim & Christian students. The “Prejudice Scale” (Revised in 2006) constructed, developed & standardized by Dr. R. L. Bharadwaj and Dr. H. Sharma was used for this study. The sample is further divided into male and female students. The obtained data were analyzed with the help of ‘Mean’, ‘SD’ & ‘t’-TEST. The result of the present study shows that there is a significant difference between the groups on the basis of area like rural and urban. Whereas the researcher found an insignificant difference on the basis of religion like Hindu, Muslim and Christian and on the basis of gender like male and female in their prejudice Behavior at 0.05 levels of significance.

INTRODUCTION

Education in the largest sense is an act or experience that has a formative effect on mind, character or physical ability of an individual. “Prejudice” means a fixed and unreasonable

behavior or unfair fixed opinions. The structure of prejudices in the form of multidimensional phenomena include favorable or unfavorable beliefs of judgments; hostile to or in favor of action, and to another group is a composite of stereo- types, pattern of discrimination, intolerance along with negative conceptions, feelings and actions.

CONCEPT OF BEHAVIOUR

According to oxford advanced learner's Dictionary: Behavior means the way that somebody behaves, especially towards other people. Many psychologists believe that behavior of a person depends on his culture, religion, caste, sex etc. Behavior of a person also changes according to their society and culture. So behavior of a person changes from one place to another ; one region to another region; one religion to another; one caste to another; one sex to another; one state to another; one country to another country and one community to another community. There are many factors for affecting human behavior, i.e., Race, Sex, sexual Orientation, Religion/Religious Affiliation, Social Class and Culture.

PREJUDICE BEHAVIOUR

The word or term “**Prejudice**”, in derived from the Latin word “Prejudicial” which means a Premature judgment formation before due consideration of the facts. It is also known as a preconceived opinion or bias against a person or thing. According to **oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary**: Prejudice means as unreasonable dislike of or preference for a person, group, custom etc., especially when it is based on their race, religion, sex etc. Prejudice (or for deeming) is making a judgment or assumption about someone or something before having enough knowledge to be able to do so with guaranteed accuracy, or “**judging a book by its cover**”. Prejudice, the word is most often used to refer to preconceived judgments toward people or a person because of race, social class, ethnicity, age, disability, obesity, religion, sexual orientation, or other personal characteristics. Thus, prejudice refers to any judgment which happens to be a prejudgment or preconceived opinion, or bias against, or unsavory, or a predetermined attitude, or idea, or sentiment made without adequate evidences which are usually emotionally colored towards some person, things, actions, objects, certain kinds of loyalty to one's or other group. Even it is also apparent that amount of prejudice vary from individual to individual and group to group in complex societies.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

It is evident that all forms of prejudices are taught, (**Bonner, 1953**) and they are influence by a variety of factors. Many researches pay more emphasis on religious affiliation as one of the factor of prejudices. Researcher conducted in Indian socio- cultural settings show that Muslim possesses more prejudices than Hindus (**Adinarayan, 1953; Chaudhary, 1958; Hassan, 1975, 1978, Hassan and Singh, 1973, Enayatullah, 1980, Singh, 1980**). Whereas **Natraj (1962)** found that Hindus have more conservative socio- economic attitude and economic conservation (**Sarkar and Hasan, 1973**) than Muslims. There was more mistrust among Hindus than Muslims (**Chatterjee, 1967**). To say in more general term religious people posses more prejudices than non- religious ones (**Adorno, 1950; Allport and Ross, 1967**). In another researches, it was found that post- graduate students poses more prejudice towards Harijan than under graduate students (**Sinha and Sinha, 1960**). **Berkowitz, 1959**, found that college girls when subjected to frustration, tends to displace their aggression towards their mates. Therefore, in another study, it was noted that caste consciousness grows earlier in rural children than urban ones (**Singh, 1960**) and urban people have more religious and sex- prejudices (**Chatterjee, 1973**). Rural Christians possess more prejudices than urban ones (**Hassan, 1976, 1977**).

The investigator has made a conscious effort to make a review of the available literature on the dependent & independent variables. Some related studies have been mentioned below: **Devine, et al., (1989)** has conducted a study on “Stereotypes and Prejudice: Their Automatic and Controlled Components”. Three studies tested basic assumptions derived from a theoretical model based on the dissociation of automatic and controlled processes involved in prejudice. **Shafranske, et al., (1990)** has conducted a study on “Clinical Psychologists’ Religious and Spiritual Orientations and Their Practice of Psychotherapy”. The study examined the nature of 107 female and 299 male clinical psychologists’ (age: 29-88years) religiousness and spirituality, attitudes towards religiousness, use of interventions of a religious nature in psychotherapy, and tanning regarding religious and spiritual issues. **Journal of Counseling and Development (1991)** has conducted a study on “College Students” and measures attitudes of 293 freshmen college students using revised Situational Attitude Scale (SAS) student-athlete.

Timothy, D. Radloff et al., (2002) has carried a study on “The Social Constructions of Prejudice among Black and White College Students”. **Lipset, et al., (2005)** has undertaken a research on “Prejudice and Society”. In this research Prejudice can be define exclusively in terms of human behavior which defines or attempts to deny equality of opportunity or status to certain racial, religious, or ethnic groups. **Graham, Thornicroft et al., (2007)** has undertaken a research on “Stigma: Ignorance, Prejudice or Discrimination?” The term stigma refers to problems to knowledge (ignorance), attitudes (prejudice) and behavior (discrimination). **Glaser, Jack et al., (2008)** has conducted a study on “Implicit Motivation to Control Prejudice.” Therefore, the need of examine current prevalence of Prejudice Behavior and its correlates had prompted this research to be undertaken.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To be determined the prejudice Behavior of college going students.
- 2) To examine the prejudice Behavior of rural and urban college going students.
- 3) To find out the prejudice Behavior of rural Hindu and urban Hindu college going students.
- 4) To assess the prejudice Behavior of rural Muslim and urban Muslim college going students.
- 5) To study the prejudice Behavior of rural Christian and urban Christian college going students
- 6) To assess the prejudice Behavior of rural boys and urban boys college going students.
- 7) To find out the prejudice Behavior of rural girls and urban girls college going students.

HYPOTHESES

- H01:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural and urban college going students.
- H02:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Hindu and urban Hindu college going students.
- H03:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Muslim and urban Muslim college going students.
- H04:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Christian and urban Christian college going students.
- H05:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural boys and urban boys college going students.
- H06:-** There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural girls and urban girls college going students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY & SAMPLING PROCEDURES

For present research work, the researcher has made study on college going students in relation to their prejudice Behavior. But, the study was limited to a particular geographical area to facilitate appropriate sample selection and to avoid bias. In the present study as per need the researcher has randomly selected 120 students from 6 different rural and 6 urban colleges from the areas of Durg and Bhilai city based on Hindu, Muslim and Christian boys and girls. The investigator has selected the sample by random sampling method for research work. In order to collect the data, the investigator chooses the disproportionate stratified random sampling procedure or technique.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study is limited to Durg and Bhilai City of C.G. State. For this study the prejudice Behavior of college going boys and girls are being measured. The present study deals with not more than 10 colleges of urban areas and 10 from rural areas and limited to only 120 college going students as sample.

TOOLS USED

The tools used by the investigator in the present study was “prejudice scale” (Pr scale) developed by Dr. R. L. Bharadwaj and Dr. H. Sharma to measure the prejudice Behavior of college going students. The statistical technique of correlation and critical ratio for each item were applied for item analysis & at .01 levels of significance was set for final selection of items. The final form of the scale has 36 items relating to different areas of prejudices and possess the capacity to evoke the response correctly. The coefficient of reliability has been determined by using the following two methods: The test- retest method (N=100) has been employed to determine the temporal stability of the scale. The product moment correlation between test and retest scores has been found to be .69 and by applying the split- half method (Gutman Formula), the reliability coefficient of the scale has been found to be .94 (N=100). Validity of the scale has been also determined by two methods: Theoretical validity of the scale has been found to .83 (under root of reliability coefficient) and Construct validity of the scale has estimated with the prejudice scale of Jahan, Q. et. al., (1988) and that comes to .66.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

After the collection of data from the selection sample, the scoring is done, and then the raw score is converted in to standard scores. The researcher analyzed the collected data by finding Mean, Standard Deviation and “t-value” to find out and measure the prejudice behavior of college going students belonging to Hindu, Muslim and Christian religions.

ADMINISTRATION OF THE TOOL & DATA COLLECTION

It is self administering scale suitable for individual and group testing. It also should be emphasized that all item have to be answered on any one of the five alternatives given for each item. It is also advisable that the tester should give a clear instruction to the tested in regard to community, caste, or religion for which the tester desires their responses for it is extremely important for the sake of this particular test. The scoring of the prejudice scale is very easy and of quantitative nature. Each item of the scale has five alternative answers and the subject has tick (✓) at any one out of five alternatives. Five alternatives for each item shall provide the score 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 from left to right (i.e., from not agreeable to the least one).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

H01:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural and urban college going students.

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL	60	89.83	19.78	1.98	SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN	60	92.54	22.55		
		df =118		p <0.05		

The above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural and urban) are insignificantly different in their prejudice behavior. On the basis of the result, our proposed hypothesis is rejected. So, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural and urban college going students.

H02:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Hindu and urban Hindu college going students.

The above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural Hindu and urban Hindu) are

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL HINDU	20	88	23.47	2.02	IN SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN HINDU	20	94	23		
		df = 38		p > 0.05		

significantly different in their prejudice Behavior. On the basis of the result, our proposed hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural and urban Hindu college going students.

H03:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Muslim and urban Muslim college going students.

The

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL MUSLIM	20	84	17.86	2.02	IN SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN MUSLIM	20	89	17.15		
		df = 38		p > 0.05		

above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural Muslim and urban Muslim students) have no significant difference in their prejudice Behavior. On the basis of the result, our proposed hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural Muslim and urban Muslim college going students.

H04:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural Christian and urban Christian college going students.

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL CHRISTIAN	20	101	15.62	2.02	IN SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN	20	100.5	13.76		

	CHRISTIAN					
		df = 38	p >0.05			

The above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural Christian and urban Christian students) have no significant difference in their prejudice Behavior. On the basis of the result, our proposed hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there does not exist any significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural Christian and urban Christian college going students.

H05:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural boys and urban boys' college going students.

The above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural boys and urban boys' students) have no significant difference in their prejudice Behavior. On the basis of the result, our

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL BOYS	30	95.33	21.37	2.00	IN SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN BOYS	30	98.33	21.34		
		df = 58	p >0.05			

proposed hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural boys and urban boys' college going students.

H06:- There exists no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior of rural girls and urban girls' college going students.

SL NO.	GROUP	N	M	S.D.	"t"	REMARK
1	RURAL GIRLS	30	94.33	19.82	2.00	IN SIGNIFICANT
2	URBAN GIRLS	30	96.33	23.98		
		df = 58	p >0.05			

The above statistical finding shows that the two groups (rural girls and urban girls' students) have no significant difference in their prejudice Behavior. On the basis of the result, our

proposed hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the prejudice Behavior among rural girls and urban girls' college going students.

MAJOR FINDINGS

On the basis of area and religion a significant difference was found out. But on the contrary the researcher found no significant difference by community, by caste & by religion of the students from both areas in their prejudice Behavior. Whereas the researcher found an insignificant difference on the basis of religion like Hindu, Muslim and Christian and on the basis of gender like male and female in their prejudice Behavior at 0.05 levels of significance.

CONCLUSION

From the above study the researcher come to the conclusion that 'Prejudice' is an opinion or judgment formed without due examination. Thus, it can be said conclusively that prejudices are of certain inevitable features of human society and play an important role in the undaunted expression of behavior, when two groups come into face to face relation.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION

The present study will enables to find out Prejudice Behavior of college going students belonging to different religions which is very significant for modern education system. The study will helps in professional success of the Teachers. It will enable the educationists and psychologists to find out solutions to prejudice behavior of college going students.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This study brings to light some new areas to be studied by the further researchers. Studies on prejudice Behavior may be extended to other educational levels i.e., primary, secondary, in district as well as state level; in other religion i.e., Jainism, Buddhism, Sickish etc. may also be taken up. Studies may be conducted to find out the influence of institution on prejudice Behavior & Study may be conducted on the effect of students attitude towards other religion (except Hindu, Muslim and Christian) etc.

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